

Design and Fabrication of Quadcopter for the Product Delivery

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Abstract

The requirement for package conveyance has expanded due to the rise of the E-commerce industry. Ramble-based innovation is the arrangement to overcome the restriction of surface street capacity in cities. Rambles can essentially decrease conveyance times and the labour related to conveyance operations. The present investigation designed and fabricated an X-Quadcopter as a low-weight, low-cost, independent flight-competent, UAV for conveying little packages. The quadcopter takes after commands from a Ground Control Station to find and explore its goal. The objective is to create a control framework for the quadcopter in arrange to empower it to realize steady flight and perform conveyance. The extent and flight time of the quadcopter is additionally tried, and the greatest stack capacity, flight time, and speed are decided. A model was manufactured, and the control framework was tried in the natural environment, and tested results showed that the quadcopter conveyance framework is fetched compelling, speedier, and more helpful than the conventional conveyance framework. The control framework stabilized the quadcopter and accomplished craved assignments in recreation. The created model endured from vibrations and flimsiness. It also contributed enormously to clamor contamination.

Keywords: X-Quadcopter; Ground Control Station; Brushless DC Motor; Propeller; Commercial Delivery.

Introduction

A quadcopter is a flying machine with four spinning blades. The rotors go around in pairs on both sides and this helps to keep the aircraft from turning or twisting. A type of drone called a quadcopter can move in six different directions. It can go in front or behind, turn left or right, and move up or down. It can also spin around these three lines. The way the aircraft flies is by making the rotors spin at different speeds [1]. Each spinning part is moved by a motor without brushes that runs on direct current. The BLDC motors can go faster or slower. They are controlled by ESCs that work very well to make sure the motors go the speed you want them to go. In Ghana, a flying machine called Zipline is being used to take blood to places where there is an urgent need for it. Big technology companies have tried using drones to bring things to people as a type of delivery. A big drone delivery system has not started working yet. Companies like Amazon, UPS, and DHL are trying out their own flying robots to deliver packages [2]. They're calling them names like Parcelcopter and Prime Air. However, these projects have never become profitable enough to make them worth producing. Airplane groups in different countries have hard rules for independent drones. Civilian drones must always be in the sight of the person using them for safety reasons and other purposes. Self-flying drones need someone who can take over in case of an emergency. These rules need to be looked at again because the technology for flying drones is improving quickly and they can now have safety

features that work without someone controlling them.

Presently, the use of drones has grown a lot because of better technology. Drones are now widely used for non-military purposes. The worldwide market for commercial drones is worth around 50 billion U. S dollars and is expected to grow to about 58.4 billion US. The function of drones is getting better and have new things they can do, which means they can be used in more ways. Drones are used for lots of various purposes like taking photographs taken using a camera on an aircraft, looking for and helping people in danger, agriculture, 3D terrain mapping, patrol and military applications etc. Many researchers like the thought of using small flying machines called quadcopters to deliver things. In the future, flying machines called drones might take over some jobs of delivery trucks. This would have effects on things like how much energy is used, how safe people are, how much air pollution there is, how loud cities are, how airplanes are managed, how crowded the roads are, how cities are planned, and how people get their stuff in cities. As more businesses need things delivered in cities, there's not enough space on the roads for all the delivery trucks. Drone delivery wants to use the sky above cities to bring things to people. A good way to deliver things needs to reach every part of the cities in the country. These are the places where people do a lot of shopping and have food brought to their homes using the internet. The size of seven big cities in India is about 1240 square kilometers on average and have an average radius of 20 km. This means a drone can cover a lot of city areas if it

can fly for 20 km. But having just one delivery center for drones in the busy city is not a good idea. It would be better to have many places where drones can get orders ready to be delivered. This thesis mentions that there are four places where things can be stored for every 20 kilometers of space. This will make the drone need to fly less than 5 kilometers. Gabriel et al., [3] theoretically developed the quadrotor helicopter and tested the vehicle control and design and proved enhanced controller performance. Jia [4] studied the energy use and life cycle greenhouse gas emissions of drones for commercial package delivery. Quadcopters have been used for taking pictures and videos from above, watching over things, and finding people who need help. Drones have been used to bring medical supplies to far-away places because of COVID-19 [5]. Axel studied the reasons for delivery drones are struggling to take off [6]. Prabhjot [6] developed the technique for low-cost intelligence, surveillance and reconnaissance technology for drone using MATLAB for the application of trace changes taken place in the area. The present study is aimed to design a quadcopter that can carry a certain amount of weight and travel a certain distance. The quadcopter has a special computer called a flight controller that helps to fly and controlled with a control system using Simulink.

2. Quadcopter Components and Structure

The major components of the quadcopter drone are frame which consists of four arms, KK Flight Controller, ESC (Electronic Speed Controller), Brushless Motors, RC6 Channel RX, Propellers. A Quadcopter is a flying machine with 4

blades located at each corner of the structure. To make a drone go where you want it to, each part called a propeller can turn in different ways by itself. This helps keep the drone steady and also helps it move in the direction you want it to. In a normal quadcopter, all four spinning blades are spaced out evenly. To keep things steady, there are two sets of three rotors. One set turns to the right, while the other set turns to the left. The drone can move in different directions by adjusting the speed of its rotors. Drones can move in four different ways depending on how the four propellers work together. These movements are called throttle, pitch, roll, and yaw. Moving the drone up or down is called throttle. When a drone moves forward or backward, it is called pitching. When a drone moves in a circle around its own body, it is called rolling motion. The components of the quadcopter drone are shown in Fig.1. The KK2. 1.5 multi-Rotor controller is a flight control board for multi-rotor aircraft (Tricopters, Quadcopters, Hexcopters etc). Electronic speed controllers (ESCs) are devices that allow drone flight controllers to control and adjust the speed of the aircraft's electric motors. In cars, they are often used for retracting, extending, and positioning electrically-powered side windows. The communication between radio receiver and flight controller is wired by using the RC channel Rx transmitter. Propellers are devices that transform rotary motion into linear thrust. Battery Lithium Polymer (LIPO) rechargeable batteries are used for quadcopters because they have high specific energy and light in weight.

Fig.1 Components of the quadcopter drone(a) KK Flight Controller (b) Electronic speed controllers (c) RC6 Channel RX (d) Propellers

3. Design, Fabrication and Testing of Quadcopter
 Most of the quadcopter design are in the form of 'X' and '+'. 'X' configuration is considered to be more stable and perfect while hovering when compared with the '+' configuration mode from the design point of view[8]. A coordinate frame of the

quadcopter and the movement of the quadcopter is shown in the Fig.2 and components of frame is depicted in Table 1. Movement in horizontal frame is achieved by tilting the platform whereas vertical movement is achieved by changing the total thrust of the motors[9].

Fig.2 Quadcopter coordinate system

Table 1. Components of Quadcopter frame

Components of Quadcopter frame	Dimensions (mm)
Length of Arms	215
Dimensions of arms	40 x 13 x 0.6
Base plate dimensions (Length of vertical, horizontal slides and thickness)	43 x 43 x 2
Rectangular drill on base plate	25 x 35
Radius of vertical and horizontal sides of top plate and thickness	82 x 2
Radius of circular drill on top plate	1.5 x 2.0
Length and breadth of square drill	5 x 32 x 35
Distance between two motors	455
Dimensions of motor nut screw (diameter)	2, 15

The improvement of quadcopter has become little difficult due to their algorithm of control on four motors and it has become very hard to maintain the same speeds of motors without the help of electronics. In order to achieve six degrees of freedom, three rotational and translational motions are coupled together. With this six DOF and four inputs the control of motors speed has become easy for the operator to tilt the quadcopter

in required direction[10]. The four input forces of quadcopter which affects the hovering are u_1 , u_2 , u_3 and u_4 . The change in altitude of the quadcopter is done by u_1 , and change in rotation of roll angle is done by u_2 , the pitch angle is affected by u_3 and the yaw angle is controlled by u_4 . These input forces will help the operator to move the quadcopter in all directions. Each input force is calculated as per Eqns. (1), (2), (3), (4) and (5).

$$U = u_1 + u_2 + u_3 + u_4 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$u_1 = \frac{T_1 + T_2 + T_3 + T_4}{m} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$u_2 = \frac{l(-T_1 + T_2 + T_3 + T_4)}{I_1} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

$$u_3 = \frac{l(-T_1 + T_2 + T_3 - T_4)}{I_2} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

$$u_4 = \frac{l(T_1 + T_2 + T_3 + T_4)}{I_2} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Torque is generated by the motor which spins at certain angular velocity and is calculated as per Eqn. (6)

$$T = \rho A V r^2 (Nm) \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

where, ρ is real-time air density (Kg/m^3), A is propeller cross sectional area and Vr is an instantaneous peripheral velocity of rotors

Maximum motor power is calculated by the Eqn. (7)

$$P = VI \text{ (Watts) } \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

Propeller Sweep Area is calculated as per Eqn. (8)

$$\text{Sweep Area, } A = 0.25 \left(\frac{\pi^2}{4} \right) (m^2) \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

Power loading is calculated as per Eqn. (9)

$$\text{Power loading} = P \times \frac{n}{A} \text{ (mm}^3/\text{Nm) } \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

where P is the motor input power and n is the efficiency of the motor.

The quadcopter movement and control will be carried out by the KK Flight controller [6,11]. The block diagram of the quadcopter and its prototype are shown in Fig.3 and 4. The KK2. 1.5 multi-Rotor controller stabilizes the drone during flight. To do

this it takes the signal from the 6050MPU gyro/acc (roll, pitch and yaw) then passes the signal to the Atmega644PA IC. A signal from the flight controller causes the ESC to raise or lower the voltage to the motor as required, thus changing the speed of the propeller.

Fig.3 Bloch diagram of the quadcopter drone

Fig.4 Quadcopter prototype

Conclusions

The quadcopter can be used to deliver small packages.

1. The quadcopter can transport up to 700 grams to any place within a distance of 5 kilometers from where it started in less than 6 minutes.
2. The cost of delivering is much less than the regular way of delivering.
3. Delivery drones are a good idea because they don't cost much, they can get packages to people quickly, and they are easier to use. This means they will probably be used a lot for short distance deliveries.
4. To compete with regular delivery, warehouses or fulfillment centers need to be opened near where people live. In the future, we need to work on solving the issues of loud sounds, shaking, not being steady, and damage to the propeller. Reducing noise can be done by making each propeller turn at a slightly different speed. The propellers will be different sizes so they can make the same amount of push. This way makes the sound spread out more, so it seems quieter.

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